

Study of the management of LSP P1 Institutions in Increasing the Issuance of SKK-K Certificates in Kalimantan

Riyan Pramadhana¹, Irfan Prasetya²

¹ Master of Civil Engineering, Faculty of Engineering, Lambung Mangkurat University.

² Lecturer in Master of Civil Engineering, Faculty of Engineering, Lambung Mangkurat University.

Abstract:- Data from a survey by the Indonesian Central Statistics Agency in 2021 shows that there is still a massive gap between certified and uncertified construction workers, so it is necessary to accelerate the certification of human construction resources. One of the determinants of accelerating certification is the well-integrated management of LSP P1. This study aims to analyze the dominant factors that influence the management of LSP P1 and determine the right strategy for improving the management of LSP P1 to increase the issuance of construction work competency certificates. The method used in this research is a survey using a questionnaire. The sample data is taken from a population from the management of LPS P1, while the analysis method uses the Relative Important Index (RII). From the results of the study, there are three dominant factors influencing the management of LSP P1 to increase the issuance of construction work competency certificates, namely (1) Post-Transition Period Regulatory Implementation Factors, (2) LSP P1 Establishment and Assistance Factors and (3) Factors of Human Resources (HR) and Excellent Service by LSP P1. Strategies that can be recommended as assistance regarding the procedures for establishing and registering a licensed LSP P1, planning and executing work programs in providing Training and Competency Tests, increasing the printing of competency assessors, especially in the civil and architectural fields, dan conducting MoU between Polytechnic and Construction Sector Universities with Construction Services Business Entities or with the Ministry of PUPR.

Keywords:- Management of LSP P1, Construction Work Competency Certificate Improvement Strategy, RII.

I. INTRODUCTION

The main issues in infrastructure development include the limited number of certified construction workers or Human Resources (HR). Law Number 2 of 2017 mandates that every worker in the construction sector must have a Work Competency Certificate as stipulated in Article 70, paragraph (1) and paragraph (2). Currently, the number of Construction Workers or Human Resources (HR) who already have Work Competency Certificates is 622,330 (7.3%) (LPJK, June 2020) out of a total of 8.5 million Indonesian Construction Workers (BPS, 2019). In 2019 the potential number of graduates of Vocational High Schools, Polytechnics, and Higher Education was 48,559

students. According to (BPS, 2019), the number of unemployed from the level of education for Vocational Schools was 8.3%, Diploma I/II/III was 6, 9% and Bachelors as much as 6.2%, with one of the leading causes being the misalignment of competencies possessed by Vocational High Schools, Polytechnic and/or Higher Education graduates with industrial needs (BPS, 2019). Survey data from the Central Statistics Agency for 2021 shows that Indonesian construction workers have exceeded 8.5 million people. Of this amount, only 9.6%, or under 10% of the construction workforce or human resources, have work competency certificates. There is still a massive gap between certified and uncertified construction workers, so it is necessary to accelerate the certification of construction workers or human resources. In addition, the data of the Independent Intensive Learning Information System in the Construction Sector (SIBIMA), although it is known that there has been a significant increase from 2017 to 2020, of the 4.9 million workers or construction human resources, only 3% are certified (SIBIMA, 2020). Of these figures, human resources come from graduates and prospective graduates of Polytechnics and Universities in the field of construction services in Indonesia. It can be concluded from these conditions that the number of qualified human resources in construction work still needs to be increased. Continuous efforts are made to carry out the Certification Test so that the implementation of construction in Indonesia can produce better quality construction and have competitiveness at the national and international levels.

The role of printing/producing a competency-certified workforce has shifted in authority/duty, initially served by the Construction Services Development Institute (LPJK). In 2022 it will become the task of the Professional Certification Institute (LSP), wherewith the growth of LSP-LSP, it is hoped that the gap in Competency certificates can be filled quickly and with quality. The Certification Test for construction workers or HR can be carried out by LSP from Educational Institutions or Competency Test Technical Committees registered by the Minister, in this case, the Minister of Public Works and Public Housing. Based on the results of data collection from the Banjarmasin Region V Construction Service Center in early 2022, the number of LSP P1 established by Polytechnics and Universities in the Construction Sector in Kalimantan still needs to be increased. There are only about 6 (six) Polytechnics that already have LSP P1, and only some of them have been in the process of being recorded on the PUPR licensing portal. LSP P1 in question is a First Party Professional Certification Institution established by an education and or training institution with the

primary objective of carrying out work competency certification for competency-based education/training participants and/or human resources from the network of its parent institution, according to the scope provided by BNSP. Based on PP Number 14 of 2021 concerning Amendments to Government Regulation Number 22 of 2020 concerning Regulations for Implementing Law Number 2 of 2017 concerning Construction Services, Article 28A to Article 28C explains that the construction workforce meets work competency standards and is required to have construction work competency certificate which has been recorded through the Integrated Construction Services Information System. The ownership of work construction certificate competency must be under the classification, sub-classification, and position qualifications that refer to the provisions of the laws and regulations. A construction work competency certificate issued by LSP, which is given a license by an independent institution regulated by legislation in the field of professionalism, is recognized as a construction work competency certificate.

The difference from several similar studies that were conducted before, although both examined the relationship with the increase in competency certificates, this study focused more on the management of LSP P1 in increasing the issuance of construction work competency certificates, especially for graduates (fresh graduates) with a maximum of 2 (two) years and candidates Polytechnic and Higher Education graduates in the field of construction carried out by LSP P1. The review is based on PP Number 14 of 2021 concerning Amendments to Government Regulation Number 22 of 2020 concerning Regulations for Implementing Law Number 2 of 2017 concerning Construction Services, article 28A to Article 28C states that the construction workforce must meet work competency standards and must have construction work competency certificate that has been recorded through SIJKT. The method in this study will evaluate the factors that can influence the management of LSP P1 to increase the issuance of construction work competency certificates at Construction Polytechnics and Universities in Kalimantan. As previously stated, currently, only LSP has a role in producing/producing a competency-certified workforce. LSP P1 from Higher Education or Polytechnic institutions certainly has an excellent opportunity

to produce competency-certified workers. This research is expected to increase the number of LSP P1 in the Kalimantan region, and a management strategy for LSP P1 can also be developed to increase the number of certified competency workers. The results of this study are expected to be a solution to overcoming problems in human construction resources which still need to be improved in the Kalimantan region.

II. RESEARCH METHOD

➤ *Research Approach*

This study aims to determine the right strategy to improve the management of LSP P1 in increasing the issuance of construction work competency certificates in the Construction HR certification process, especially those at Polytechnics and Universities in Kalimantan, which LSP P1 carries out in collaboration with the Banjarmasin Region V Construction Service Center. The steps of the research carried out are as follows:

- Preliminary study
- Literature Review
- Determination of the dominant factors that influence the management of LSP P1 in increasing the issuance of construction work competency certificate
- Determination of the right strategy to improve the management of LSP P1 in increasing the issuance of construction work competency certificates at Polytechnics and Universities in Kalimantan at the Banjarmasin Region V Construction Service Center.

➤ *Primary Data Collection*

➤ *Questionnaire*

This study's data analysis was based on data processing obtained through questionnaire data. The data collected is a measure of clear indicators obtained through distributing questionnaires to respondents in this study, namely educational institutions at the Polytechnic and Higher Education levels in Construction in Kalimantan, which have LSP P1, as shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Identify Influential Factors

Variables/Indicators	
LSP P1 Establishment and Assistance	Socialization and internal funding in establishing LSP P1 in the Construction Sector towards increasing the issuance of construction work competency certificates (SKK-K) - (X1)
	Socialization and external funding in establishing LSP P1 in the Construction Sector to increase the issuance of construction work competency certificates (SKK-K) - (X2)
	The role of BNSP in assisting the establishment of LSP P1 in the Construction Sector towards increasing the issuance of construction work competency certificates (SKK-K) - (X3)
	The role of LPJK in assisting the establishment of LSP P1 in the Construction Sector towards increasing the issuance of construction work competency certificates (SKK-K) - (X4)
	The role of BJKW in assisting the establishment of LSP P1 in the Construction Sector towards increasing the issuance of construction work competency certificates (SKK-K) - (X5)
Implementation of Post Transitional Regulations	Formation of LSP P1 in the Construction Sector to increase the issuance of construction work competency certificate (SKK-K) - (X6)
	Licensing of LSP P1 in the Construction Sector at LPJK to increase the issuance of construction work competency certificate (SKK-K) - (X7)

	The number of Prospective Graduates facilitated by LSP P1 in the Construction Sector has increased the issuance of construction work competency certificates (SKK-K) - (X8)
	The number of graduates facilitated by LSP P1 in the Construction Sector has increased the issuance of construction work competency certificates (SKK-K) - (X9)
Implementation of Competency Test by LSP P1	Costs in carrying out the competency test facilitated by LSP P1 in the Construction Sector towards increasing the issuance of construction work competency certificate (SKK-K) - (X10)
	Completeness of Facilities and Infrastructure in carrying out the competency test facilitated by LSP P1 in the Construction Sector towards increasing the issuance of construction work competency certificate (SKK-K) - (X11)
Human Resources (HR) and Excellent Service by LSP P1	Availability of the number of assessors in the construction sector at LSP P1 in the Construction Sector towards the increase in the issuance of construction work competency certificates (SKK-K) - (X12)
	Availability of Competency Test Sites at LSP P1 in the Construction Sector towards increasing the issuance of construction work competency certificates (SKK-K) - (X13)
	A large number of types of construction work competency certificates issued by LSP P1 in the Construction Sector has increased the issuance of construction work competency certificates (SKK-K) - (X14)
	The LSP P1 Process in the Construction Sector registers with LPJK the increase in the issuance of construction work competency certificates (SKK-K) - (X15)
	LSP P1 Process in the Construction Sector to obtain LPJK recommendations for increasing the issuance of construction work competency certificate (SKK-K) - (X16)
	LSP P1 Process in the Construction Sector to obtain a BNSP license to increase the issuance of construction work competency certificate (SKK-K) - (X17)
	LSP P1 Process in the Construction Sector for recording at LPJK towards increasing the issuance of construction work competency certificate (SKK-K) - (X18)
	The maximum service performed by LSP P1 in the Construction Sector towards increasing the issuance of construction work competency certificate (SKK-K) - (X19)
	There is an MoU/KSO between Polytechnics and Universities in the Field of Construction and Construction Service Business Entities towards increasing the issuance of construction work competency certificates (SKK-K) - (X20)
	Training Program and Competency Test by related Stakeholders
Training Program and Competency Test for Prospective Graduates to increase the issuance of construction work competency certificate (SKK-K) - (X22)	
Training Program and Competency Test for Graduates to increase the issuance of construction work competency certificate (SKK-K) - (X23)	
Additional Competency Training for Prospective Graduates to increase the issuance of construction work competency certificate (SKK-K) - (24)	
Additional Competency Training for Graduates to increase the issuance of construction work competency certificate (SKK-K) - (X25)	
SIBIMA Construction Training for Prospective Graduates to increase the issuance of construction work competency certificate (SKK-K) - (26)	
SIBIMA Construction Training for Graduates on increasing the issuance of construction work competency certificate (SKK-K) - (27)	

Respondents' answers were selected based on the choice of answers to assess the level of importance of the factors given as many as five levels using a Likert scale, as shown in Table 2.

Table 2: Respondent's Answer Options

Scoring	Answer	Code
1	Very unimportant	STP
2	Not important	TP
3	Quite important	CP
4	Important	P
5	Very important	SP

➤ *Respondents*

Respondents in this study were the Chairperson of LSP P1 or the Management of LSP P1 at Construction Field Polytechnics and Universities in Kalimantan, Heads of Civil Engineering Study Programs at Universities in Kalimantan and Heads of Civil Engineering Departments at Polytechnics in Kalimantan. The objectives obtained through the respondents are the dominant factors that influence the management of LSP P1 in increasing the issuance of construction work competency certificates for Construction Human Resources at Polytechnics and Universities in Kalimantan. Respondents in this study are as follows:

- Head of LSP/Management of LSP Construction Field (Polytechnic and College) as many as 26 people;
- Head of Civil Engineering Department (Polytechnic) as many as ten people; and
- Head of the Civil Engineering Study Program (Faculty of College Engineering) as many as 16 people.

➤ *Validity and Reliability Test*

The validity test uses a correlation coefficient significance test at a significance level of 0.05, meaning an item is considered valid if it correlates significantly with the total score. The significance test was carried out by comparing the value of r count with r table for the degree of freedom (df) = n - 2, in this case, n is the number of samples.

This study's measurement of the reliability test used one shot or only one measurement. In one-shot measurement, the measurement is only done once, and then the results are compared with other questions or measured by the correlation between the answers to questions. Statistical tests can be used to measure reliability, namely Cronbach's Alpha equation (α).

➤ *Observation*

Observation or direct observation of the research object is carried out for each indicator that influences the construction HR certification test process following the latest regulations. The aim is to determine what influences the management of LSP P1 in increasing the issuance of construction work competency certificates for Construction Human Resources at Polytechnics and Universities in the Field of Construction in Kalimantan in the Implementation of Post-Transition Period Certification.

➤ *Interview*

The data was obtained by conducting interviews through an open questionnaire to the Banjarmasin Region V Construction Service Center, namely conducting interviews directly with office holders such as the Head of the BJKW Implementation Section V Banjarmasin. The aim is to obtain supporting data that influence the management of LSP P1 in increasing the issuance of construction work competency certificates for Construction Human Resources at Polytechnics and Universities in the Field of Construction in Kalimantan in the Implementation of Post-Transition Period Certification.

➤ *Secondary Data*

Secondary data is additional or supporting data to strengthen research results. The data uses material not from the first source to obtain data or information to answer the problem under study.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

➤ *Instrument Test*

➤ *Validity test*

Data validity was tested using item-total correlation with Spearman's correlation coefficient using the Microsoft Excel 2016 program. For n = 52, the r-Table (critical) value used was 0.279, meaning that if r-Count > 0.279, then the question is valid. The results of calculating the validity test can be seen in Table 3.

Table 3: Validity Test Results with Spearman's Correlation Coefficient

Factor	Question Code	r-Count	r-Table	Information
LSP P1 Establishment and Assistance	X1	0.771	0.279	Valid
	X2	0.726		Valid
	X3	0.632		Valid
	X4	0.658		Valid
	X5	0.740		Valid
Implementation of Post Transitional Regulations	X6	0.782	0.279	Valid
	X7	0.808		Valid
	X8	0.861		Valid
	X9	0.861		Valid
Implementation of Competency Test by LSP P1	X10	0.897	0.279	Valid
	X11	0.865		Valid
Human Resources (HR) and Excellent Service by LSP P1	X12	0.479	0.279	Valid
	X13	0.663		Valid
	X14	0.686		Valid
	X15	0.668		Valid
	X16	0.774		Valid
	X17	0.745		Valid
	X18	0.818		Valid
	X19	0.589		Valid
	X20	0.571		Valid
Training Program and Competency Test by related Stakeholders	X21	0.682	0.279	Valid
	X22	0.757		Valid
	X23	0.719		Valid
	X24	0.797		Valid
	X25	0.816		Valid
	X26	0.728		Valid
	X27	0.781		Valid

Based on the validity test of the 27 question variable items from five factors, it was found that all r-count values were higher than r-tables, so question variable items were declared valid and could be used in the following analysis stage. Furthermore, to determine the reliability of the data, it is necessary to carry out the stages of reliability testing on all data used.

➤ *Reliability Test*

Reliability testing stages need to be carried out to know the reliability of all data used and whether the measuring instruments are accurate, stable, and consistent. The instrument used in this study can be reliable if it has a Cronbach's Alpha value (α) > 0.70. The questionnaire results on 52 respondents in this study showed that each variable question item declared valid would be tested for reliability. The results of the reliability test on all question variable items can be shown in Table 4.

Table 4: Reliability Test Results with Cronbach's Alpha (α)

Number of Variables	Correlation Number Value Cronbach's Alpha (α)	Reliability Level
27	0.929	Very Strong

Based on the results of the reliability testing of all the question variables, the value of Cronbach's Alpha (α) is obtained at the correlation coefficient interval of 0.70 to 0.90, which shows a solid interpretation of the level of reliability or high reliability, which is a correlation value of 0.929.

➤ *Rating of Factors Influencing LSP P1 Management in Increasing SKK-K Issuance*

This study determines the ranking based on the Relative Important Index (RII) value. RII is used to determine the level of the factors that influence the increase in the issuance of SKK-K

at Construction Polytechnics and Universities in Kalimantan. As an example of the calculation of question X7 as follows:

$$(RII)(Xm) = i = 1 \frac{\sum(n_{ix} \text{Bobot } i)}{n}$$

or

$$RII = \frac{\sum w}{AN} = \frac{1n_1 + 2n_2 + 3n_3 + 4n_4 + 5n_5}{5(n_1 + n_2 + n_3 + n_4 + n_5)}$$

$$RII_{x7} = \frac{1 \cdot 0 + 2 \cdot 0 + 3 \cdot 0 + 4 \cdot 14 + 5 \cdot 38}{5(0 + 0 + 0 + 14 + 38)} = 0,9462$$

Table 5: Rating of Factors Influencing LSP P1 Management in Increasing SKK-K Issuance

Code	Variable	Total Weight	RII value	RII rating	Criteria Score
X7	Licensing of LSP P1 in the Construction Sector at LPJK to increase the issuance of SKK-K	246	0.9462	1	Very important
X3	The role of BNSP in assisting the establishment of LSP P1 in the Construction Sector towards increasing the issuance of SKK-K	243	0.9346	2	Very important
X6	Formation of LSP P1 in the Construction Sector to increase the issuance of SKK-K	243	0.9346	3	Very important
X12	Availability of the number of assessors in the construction sector at LSP P1 in the Construction Sector towards the increase in the issuance of SKK-K	240	0.9231	4	Very important
X20	There is an MoU/KSO between Polytechnics and Universities in the Field of Construction and Construction Service Business Entities toward increasing the issuance of SKK-K	240	0.9231	5	Very important
X8	The number of Prospective Graduates facilitated by LSP P1 in the Construction Sector has increased the issuance of SKK-K	239	0.9192	6	Very important
X13	Availability of Competency Test Sites at LSP P1 in the Construction Sector towards increasing the issuance of SKK-K	239	0.9192	7	Very important
X9	The number of graduates facilitated by LSP P1 in the Construction Sector has increased the issuance of SKK-K	238	0.9154	8	Very important
X23	Training Program and Competency Test for Graduates to increase the issuance of SKK-K	237	0.9115	9	Very important
X11	Completeness of Facilities and Infrastructure in carrying out the competency test facilitated by LSP P1 in the Construction Sector towards increasing the issuance of SKK-K	235	0.9038	10	Very important
X22	Training Program and Competency Test for Prospective Graduates to increase the issuance of SKK-K	235	0.9038	11	Very important
X19	The maximum service performed by LSP P1 in the Construction Sector towards increasing the issuance of SKK-K	234	0.9000	12	Very important
X21	Link and Match Program for Prospective Graduates to increase the issuance of SKK-K	234	0.9000	13	Very important
X1	Socialization and internal funding in establishing LSP P1 in the Construction Sector toward increasing the issuance of SKK-K	232	0.8923	14	Very important
X2	Socialization and external funding in establishing LSP P1 in the Construction Sector to increase the issuance of SKK-K	232	0.8923	15	Very important
X17	LSP P1 Process in the Construction Sector to obtain a BNSP license to increase the issuance of SKK-K	232	0.8923	16	Very important
X26	SIBIMA Construction Training for Prospective Graduates to increase the issuance of SKK-K	232	0.8923	17	Very important
X27	SIBIMA Construction Training for Graduates on increasing the issuance of SKK-K	231	0.8885	18	Very important
X5	The role of BJKW in assisting the establishment of LSP P1 in the Construction Sector towards increasing the issuance of SKK-K	230	0.8846	19	Very important

X24	Additional Competency Training for Prospective Graduates to increase the issuance of SKK-K	230	0.8846	20	Very important
X25	Additional Competency Training for Graduates to increase the issuance of SKK-K	230	0.8846	21	Very important
X4	The role of LPJK in assisting the establishment of LSP P1 in the Construction Sector towards increasing the issuance of SKK-K	227	0.8731	22	Very important
X10	Costs in carrying out the competency test facilitated by LSP P1 in the Construction Sector towards increasing the issuance of SKK-K	226	0.8692	23	Very important
X14	The large number of types of SKK-K issued by LSP P1 in the Construction Sector has increased the issuance of SKK-K	226	0.8692	24	Very important
X18	LSP P1 Process in the Construction Sector for recording at LPJK towards increasing the issuance of SKK-K	222	0.8538	25	Very important
X15	The LSP P1 Process in the Construction Sector registers with LPJK the increase in the issuance of SKK-K	220	0.8462	26	Very important
X16	LSP P1 Process in the Construction Sector to obtain LPJK recommendations for increasing the issuance of SKK-K	218	0.8385	27	Very important

The results of RII's calculations related to the factors that influence the management of LSP P1 towards increasing the issuance of SKK-K at Polytechnics and Universities in the Field of Construction in Kalimantan show that 27 variables out of the five factors all have critical assessment criteria.

➤ *Analysis and Discussion*

➤ *Determination of Dominant Factors*

From the analysis results, these 27 variables have essential criteria. Then 27 variables from the analysis results must be considered for improvement or research. However, like the initial research hypothesis, the current problem is the limited licensed LSP P1. From the results of observations and studies of secondary data, only a few Polytechnics and Universities in the Field of Construction in Kalimantan have established LSP P1, namely only five Polytechnics with LSP P1. Of the five Polytechnics, it is known that 3 Polytechnics with schemes in the construction sector, and 2 Polytechnics with schemes outside the construction sector. Furthermore, those who have received recommendations from LPJK PUPR and are applying for licenses from BNSP are from only 3 Polytechnics, namely Banjarmasin State Polytechnic, Samarinda State Polytechnic, and Pontianak State Polytechnic.

Meanwhile, when viewed from the top five factors that have the highest RII value from the first to the fifth rank, as follows:

- Factors for Implementing Post-Transition Period Regulations, with the variable being licensed by LSP P1 in the Construction Sector at LPJK to increase the issuance of SKK-K;
- LSP P1 Establishment and Assistance Factors, with the variable role of BNSP in assisting the establishment of LSP P1 in the Construction Sector towards increasing the issuance of SKK-K;
- Factors for Implementing Post-Transition Period Regulations, with the variable forming LSP P1 in the Construction Sector to increase the issuance of SKK-K;
- Factors of Human Resources (HR) and Excellent Service by LSP P1, with the variable availability of the number of assessors in the construction sector at LSP P1 in the

Construction Sector towards an increase in the issuance of SKK-K; and

- Factors of Human Resources (HR) and Excellent Service by LSP P1, with an MoU/KSO between Polytechnics and Universities in the Construction Sector and Construction Service Business Entities (BUJK), towards increasing the issuance of SKK-K.

Of the five top-ranking factors mentioned, the variables are closely related to the management and establishment of LSP P1. The five top-ranking variables are obtained from the three dominant factors that influence the management of LSP P1 in increasing the issuance of SKK-K, as follows:

- Regulatory Implementation Factors After the Transitional Period,
- LSP P1 Establishment and Assistance Factors, and
- Factors of Human Resources (HR) and Excellent Service by LSP P1.

➤ *Systems Approach*

After calculating all variables and knowing the dominant factors that influence the management and establishment of LSP P1 on increasing the issuance of SKK-K, the criteria for determining the most important factors or strengthening explanations related to these factors, whether they can be stated as top priorities can be carried out in a systemic approach. The initial step in confirming the intended system is that the existing variables can be divided into those with an internal effect and those with an external effect on the management of LSP P1. Can be seen in Fig. 1 LSP P1 management system approaches from research results.

Fig. 1: LSP P1 Management System Approach

As described in the explanation above, it is known that these 27 variables are crucial in improving the management of LSP P1. However, this study will focus on variables directly related to establishing LSP P1 according to the five dominant variables found. For this reason, further discussion will be specifically related to these five variables in this system approach.

➤ *External Factors*

- Licensing of LSP P1 in the Construction Sector at LPJK to increase the issuance of SKK-K (X7).

The licensing of LSP P1 in the Construction Sector at LPJK to increase the issuance of SKK-K can be explained in the Post-Transition Period regulations, namely based on PP Number 14 of 2021 concerning Amendments to Government Regulation Number 22 of 2020 concerning Regulations for Implementing Law Number 2 of 2017 concerning Construction Services, in Article 28A to Article 28C. The intended articles explain that TKK meets work competency standards and requires SKK-K, which has been recorded through the integrated Construction Services Information System. SKK-K ownership must be in accordance with the classification, sub-classification, and position qualifications that refer to the provisions of the laws and regulations. SKK-K, issued by LSP and licensed by an independent institution regulated by legislation in the field of professionalism, is recognized as a Construction Work Competency Certificate. The independent or non-structural institution referred to in this rule is LPJK.

- *The role of BNSP in assisting the establishment of LSP P1 in the Construction Sector towards increasing the issuance of SKK-K (X3).*

From the previous explanation, it is known that several Construction Polytechnics and Universities in Kalimantan still need to have LSP P1 or have established LSP P1. This factor is quite influential in increasing the issuance of SKK-K. The limited number of Polytechnics and Colleges in the Construction Sector that have LSP P1 means competency test activities at the vocational level, especially for graduates (fresh graduates) with a maximum of 2 (two) years and prospective Polytechnic and Higher Education graduates in the Construction Sector cannot issue SKK-K independently. From these conditions, it is hoped that there will be socialization and technical guidance or mentoring workshops regarding the procedures for forming and registering a licensed LSP P1.

- *There is an MoU/KSO between Polytechnics and Universities in the Field of Construction and Construction Service Business Entities (CSBE) toward increasing the issuance of SKK-K (X20).*

In terms of increasing competence for human construction resources, this can be done in many ways. One is by making a cooperation agreement or KSO between educational institutions and CSBE. Implementation of activities that KSO strengthens will ensure that planned activities will be carried out and must be carried out according to the agreed schedule so that the acceleration to increase the

competence of human construction resources can be calculated.

➤ *Internal Factors*

- Formation of LSP P1 in the Construction Sector to increase the issuance of SKK-K (X6).

It can be seen from some of the previous explanations that there are still Construction Polytechnics and Universities in Kalimantan which do not yet have LSP P1 or have established LSP P1. Even though LSP P3 can currently serve the competency test process in collaboration with the Regional Construction Service Center, this activity requires a long time in the implementation process due to the limited number of LSP P3 who can carry out competency tests following the scheme or work position and the level required for graduates (fresh graduates) with a maximum of 2 (two) years and prospective graduates of Polytechnics and Universities in the Field of Construction.

- Availability of the number of assessors in the construction sector at LSP P1 in the Construction Sector towards an increase in the issuance of SKK-K (X12).

The critical availability of the number of assessors in each LSP, both LSP P1, LSP P2, and LSP P3, is a supporting factor for the smooth implementation of the competency test process. It is hoped that educational institutions with LSP and a limited number of assessors can increase the availability of the number of assessors according to the qualifications and classifications set by BNSP to support the competency test process according to the provisions and produce a competent construction workforce.

➤ *Treatment Priority*

Per current regulations, the main priority is to form and license LSP P1 at Polytechnics and Higher Education in the Field of Construction. One of the first steps that must be taken for those who do not have an LSP this year is to try to form an LSP Formation Team as soon as possible. The positive side of forming the Team is that it will likely play a full role in encouraging Polytechnics and Higher Education to establish LSP P1 and register with LPJK PUPR to obtain recommendations and licenses for conducting competency tests, especially in the construction sector.

➤ *Interview*

After knowing the dominant factors from the analysis results, interviews were conducted with competent assessors/experts. This study conducted interviews with the Banjarmasin Region V Construction Service Center as the organizer of the construction worker certification/competency test activities in the Kalimantan region.

➤ *LSP P1 Management Strategy in Certificate Issuance*

The strategies that can be implemented to improve the management of LSP P1 in issuing SKK-K at Polytechnics and Universities include:

- Facing regulatory changes from the Transition Period to the Post-Transition Period, the Ministry of Public Works and Public Housing, in collaboration with LPJK PUPR,

BNSP, and the Ministry of Education and Culture are expected to organize activities such as technical guidance or mentoring workshops regarding procedures for forming and registering a licensed LSP P1 and inviting representatives from Polytechnics and Universities in the Field of Construction to provide understanding and guide related parties so that they can form or establish LSP P1 until it is licensed at LPJK PUPR. With a licensed LSP P1 in each educational institution, it is expected that graduates and prospective graduates will be able to independently carry out competency tests so that when they enter the world of work, these graduates already have SKK-K according to industry needs.

- Establishing a licensed LSP P1 is obliged to plan and carry out work programs in providing Training and Certification/Competency Tests for graduates and prospective graduates of Polytechnics and Colleges in the Field of Construction periodically or properly scheduled in each different budget year. A possible strategy that can be carried out by Polytechnics and Higher Education is to require each prospective graduate and graduate (fresh graduate) for a maximum of 2 (two) years to take part in Competency Development Activities or Additional Competency Training (PKT) and Certification Tests from the Ministry of PUPR and other stakeholders. If this kind of thing can be realized every year, it will automatically increase the production of graduates who have SKK-K.
- Managers of LSP P1 from each Polytechnic and Higher Education in the Field of Construction in Kalimantan are expected to be able to print more competency assessors, especially in the civil and architectural fields, so that when carrying out competency tests carried out by LSP P1 independently, or in collaboration with other parties, they can assess with a more significant number of participants. In this way, increasing the number of assessors at LSP P1 can also increase the issuance of SKK-K.
- LSP P1 can carry out activities independently related to increasing competence to increase the issuance of SKK-K. However, sometimes not all P1 LSPs can carry out training and competency tests independently due to limitations in budget, human resources, or place of implementation. There will be restrictions on implementing activities that have been planned or targeted. However, this can be circumvented using an MoU/KSO between the Polytechnic and Higher Education in the Construction Sector and the Construction Service Business Entity (CSBE) or with the PUPR Ministry. In this case, the party in question is the Regional Construction Service Center as an extension of the center and organizer of the certification activities construction workforce in the region. That way, the competency improvement program that has been scheduled can still be carried out with collaboration between the two parties.

IV. CONCLUSION

Based on the results of research and data processing that have been done, some conclusions can be drawn as follows:

- From the results of the RII calculation of the five factors and 27 variables/indicators that influence the management of LSP P1 towards increasing the issuance of SKK-K at

Construction Polytechnics and Universities in Kalimantan. It can be seen that the three most dominant factors are as follows:

- Implementation of the Post-Transition Period Regulations with the variables, namely the licensing of LSP P1 in the Construction Sector at LPJK to increase the issuance of SKK-K and the formation of LSP P1 in the Construction Sector to increase the issuance of SKK-K.
 - Establishment and Assistance of LSP P1 with its variables, namely the role of BNSP in assisting the establishment of LSP P1 in the Construction Sector towards increasing the issuance of SKK-K.
 - Human Resources (HR) and Excellent Service by LSP P1 with the variables, namely the availability of the number of assessors in the field of construction at LSP P1 in the Construction Sector towards increasing the issuance of SKK-K and the existence of an MoU/KSO between Polytechnics and Universities in the Construction Sector and Construction Service Business Entities (CSBE) towards increasing the issuance of SKK-K.
- Recommendations given in this study, namely assistance regarding procedures for the formation and registration of licensed LSP P1, planning and carrying out work programs in providing Training and Competency Tests, increasing the printing of competency assessors, especially in the civil and architectural fields and conducting MoUs/KSOs between Polytechnics and Universities in the Construction Sector with the Construction Service Business Entity (BUJK) or with the Ministry of PUPR.

REFERENCES

- [1]. Adi, Henny Pratiwi dan Siti Ummu Adillah. (2009). *Sertifikasi Tenaga Kerja Konstruksi Sebagai Unsur Pendukung Pembangunan Infrastruktur*. Semarang: Universitas Islam Sultan Agung.
- [2]. Badan Pusat Statistik. (2019). *Survey Angkatan Kerja Nasional/Sakernas BPS 2016-2019*. Jakarta: BPS Republik Indonesia.
- [3]. Buletin Konstruksi. (2019). *Sertifikasi Tenaga Kerja Konstruksi*. Edisi 2 Tahun 2019. Jakarta: Direktorat Jenderal Bina Konstruksi Kementerian PUPR.
- [4]. Burhanuddin, Dr. Ir. Syarif. (2021). *Pelaksanaan Sertifikasi Pasca Masa Transisi*. Serpong: LPJK PUPR.
- [5]. Elyanti, Nor Azizah. (2021). *Analisis Implementasi Sertifikasi Tenaga Kerja Konstruksi Pada Balai Jasa Konstruksi Wilayah V Banjarmasin (Kalimantan)*. Tesis Magister Teknik Sipil Universitas Lambung Mangkurat. Banjarmasin.
- [6]. Jelantik, I M. Alit K. Salain, Mayun Nadiasa. (2014). *Analisis Faktor yang Mempengaruhi Tenaga Kerja Konstruksi untuk Memiliki SKA/SKT pada Kontraktor di Kabupaten*. Bandung: Jurnal Spektran, Vol. 2 No. 1 Januari 2014.
- [7]. Peraturan Pemerintah Nomor 14 tahun 2021 Tentang Perubahan Atas Peraturan Pemerintah Nomor 22 tahun 2020 Tentang Peraturan Pelaksanaan Undang-Undang Nomor 2 Tahun 2017 Tentang Jasa Konstruksi.

- [8]. Sistem Informasi Belajar Intensif Mandiri Bidang Konstruksi (SIBIMA). (2020). Jakarta: Direktorat Jenderal Bina Konstruksi Kementerian PUPR.
- [9]. Soekiman A. Fitri E. W. (2014). *Hambatan Tenaga Terampil Dalam Memperoleh Sertifikat Keterampilan di Bidang Jasa Konstruksi*. Prosiding Konteks Universitas Atma Jaya Yogyakarta: Jurusan Manajemen Proyek Konstruksi. Vol. 1, No. 8 137 - 146.
- [10]. Spearman, C. (1904). *General Intelligence Objectivity, Objectively Determined and Measured*, *American Journal of Psychology*, Vol. 15, No. 1, 201-293.
- [11]. Surat Edaran LPJK PUPR Nomor 20/SE/LPJK/2021. (2021). *Tentang Pedoman Rekomendasi Lisensi Lembaga Sertifikasi Profesi (LSP), Pencatatan Lembaga Sertifikasi Profesi (LSP) Terlisensi, serta Daftar Penyesuaian Standar Kompetensi Kerja dan Jabatan Kerja Konstruksi*. Jakarta: Kementerian PUPR.
- [12]. Surat Edaran Menteri PUPR. (2021). *Petunjuk Pelaksanaan Sertifikasi Kompetensi Kerja Konstruksi Oleh Tim Penyelenggara Sertifikasi Kompetensi Kerja Jasa Konstruksi Pada Masa Transisi*. Jakarta: Kementerian PUPR.
- [13]. Undang-Undang Nomor 2 Tahun 2017 Tentang Jasa Konstruksi.